

A SURVEY STUDY OF ADMINISTRATIVE BEHAVIOR IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS WORKING IN VARIOUS INSTITUTIONS

Dr. Shantilal Bamta*, Mr. Abhinav Sharma, Mr. Deepak Singh and Mr. Raghav Chouhan

*HOD & Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education & Sports,

Mewar University, Rajasthan, India.

Assistant Professor Department of Physical Education & Sports, Mewar University, Rajasthan,
India

ABSTRACT

Administrative behavior as the study and understanding of individual and group behavior and patterns of structure in order to help improve administrative performance and effectiveness. Administrative behavior is a term applied to the systematic study of the behavior of individuals within work groups, including an analysis of the nature of groups, the development of structures between and within groups and the process of implementing change. The definitions indicate that the principal issues addressed by administrative behavior are:- Individual behavior and performance at work; The nature and working of people in groups; The nature of social structures and administration design at work; The processes involved in adapting behavior to meet changing conditions. There is close relationship between administrative behavior and management theory and practice. Some writers suggest that administrative behavior and management are synonymous, but this is something of an over-simplification because there are many broader facts to management.

Key Words: administrative behavior, external environment, individual behavior, sociological approach, administrative culture.

1. INTRODUCTION

Administration behavior is the study of behaviors and attitudes of people in an administration. After all human behaviors and attitudes determine effectiveness of any administration. The variable outlined above provides parameters within which a number of interrelated dimensions can be identified – the individual, the group, the administration and the environment – which

collectively influence behavior in work administrations. Administrations are made up of their individual members. The individual is a central feature of administrative behavior and a necessary part of any behavioral situation, whether acting in isolation or as part of a group, in response to expectations of the administration, or as a result of the influences of the external environment. Where the needs of the individual and the demands of the administration are incompatible, this can result in frustration and conflict. It is the task of management to integrate the individual and the administration, and to provide a working environment which permits the satisfaction of individual needs as well as the attainment of administrative goals. Groups exist in all administrations and are essential to their working and performance. The administration comprises groups of people and almost everyone in an administration will be a member of one or more groups. Informal groups arise from the social needs of people within the administration. People in groups influence each other in many ways, and groups may develop their own hierarchies and leaders. Group pressures can have a major influence over the behavior and performance of individual members. An understanding of group structure and behavior complements knowledge of individual behavior and adds a further dimension to administrative behavior.

2. THE ADMINISTRATION

Individuals and groups interact within the structure of the formal administration. Structure is created by management to establish relationships between individuals and groups, to provide order and systems and to direct the efforts of the administration into goal-seeking activities. It is through the formal structure that people carry out their administrative activities in order to achieve aims and objectives. Behavior is affected by patterns of administrative structure, technology, styles of leadership and systems of management through which administrative processes are planned, directed and controlled. The focus of attention, therefore, is on the impact of administrative structure and design, and patterns of management, on the behavior of people within the administration. For example, McGhee (1996) refers to the growth in the nature and importance of administrative structures and their essence, and for greater emphasis, on business-to-business (B2B) depth or group interviewing as part of an insight into business and administrative behavior.

3. ENVIRONMENT

The administration functions as part of the broader external environment of which it is a part. The environment affects the administration through, for example, technological and scientific development, economic activity, social and cultural influences governmental actions, the effects of the operation of the administration within its environment reflect in terms of the management of opportunities and risks and the successful achievement of its aims and objectives. The increasing rate of change in environmental factors has highlighted the need to study the total administration and the processes by which the administration attempts to adapt to the external demands placed upon it. Increasing globalization means that administrations must respond to different market demands and local requirements. Globalization impacts on administrative behavior, and places greater emphasis on processes within administrations rather than functions of the administration.

4. APPROACHES TO ADMINISTRATIVE BEHAVIOR

These different dimensions provide contrasting but related approaches to the understanding of human behavior in administrations. They present a number of alternative pathways for the study of subject and level of analysis. It is possible, for example, to adopt a psychological approach with the main emphasis on the individuals of which the administration is comprised. Psychological aspects are important but, by themselves, provide too narrow an approach for the understanding of management and administrative behavior. It is also possible to adopt a sociological approach concerned with a broader emphasis on human behavior in society. Sociological aspects can be important. A number of sociology writers seem set on the purpose of criticizing traditional views of administration and management. The study of behavior can be viewed in terms of three main disciplines - psychology, sociology and anthropology. All three disciplines have made an important contribution to the field of administrative behavior. Psychologists are concerned, broadly speaking, with the study of human behavior, with traits of the individual and membership of small social groups. The main focus of attention is on the individual as a whole person, or what can be termed the 'personality system', including, for example, perception, attitudes and motives. Sociologists are more concerned with the study of social behavior, relationships among social groups and societies, and the maintenance of order.

The main focus attention is on analysis of social structures and positions in those structures – for example, the relationship between the behavior of leaders and followers. Anthropologists are more concerned with the science of mankind and the study of human behavior as a whole. As far as administrative behavior is concerned, the main focus of attention is on the cultural system, the beliefs, customs, ideas and values within a group and the comparison of behavior among different cultures - for example, the importance of Muslim women wearing trousers to work. People learn to depend on their culture to give them security and stability, and they can suffer adverse reactions to unfamiliar environments. The contribution of relevant aspects of psychology, social and anthropology aid our understanding of the behavior of people in work administrations, and underpin the field of administrative behavior. Behavioral science attempts to structure administrations in order to secure the optimum working environment. Administrative Behavior individuals and the realization of their potential. Emphasis is on the application of relevant aspects of psychological and sociological theory and practice, and cultural influences, to problems of administration and management in the work situation. In terms of the applications of behavioral science to the management of people, we need also to consider the relevance and applications of philosophy, ethics and the law.

5. ADMINISTRATIVE CULTURE

Psychologists say that every individual has what they call personality. An individual personality is made up of a set of relatively permanent and stable traits. When we describe someone as warm, innovative, relaxed or conservative, we are describing personality traits. An administration, too, has personality which we call its culture. Administrative culture is a system of shared meaning within an administration that determines, in large degree, how employees act (Robbins and Coulter, 1996). Administrative culture represents a common perception held by the administration's employees. Just as tribal cultures have rules and taboos that dictate how members act toward one another and outsiders, administrations have cultures that govern how their employees should behave. In every administration, there are systems or patterns of values, symbols, rituals, myths and practices that have evolved over time. These shared values determine, in large degree, what employees see and how they respond to their world. When confronted with a problem, the administrative culture restricts what employees can do by suggesting the correct way with which the administration solves the problem. Research suggests

that there are seven dimensions that, in aggregate, capture the essence of an administration's culture. The dimensions are: -

- Innovation and risk taking: The degree to which employees are encouraged to be innovative and to take risks.
- Attention to detail: The degree to which employees are expected to exhibit precision, analysis and attention.
- Outcome orientation: The degree to which administration focus on the result or outcomes rather than on the techniques and processes used to achieve those outcomes.
- People orientation: The degree to which management decisions take into consideration the effect of outcomes on people with the administration.
- Team orientation: The degree to which work activities are organized around teams rather than individuals.
- Aggressiveness: The degree to which people are aggressive and competitive rather than easygoing.
- Stability: The degree to which administrative activities emphasize the maintaining of the status.

6. ADMINISTRATIVE BEHAVIOR

However, administrations differ from one to another on the strength of their cultures. Administrations with strong cultures have key values which are intensely held and widely shared. Such administrations have greater influence on employees than do those with the weak cultures. The more employees accept the administration's key values and the greater their commitment to those values, the stronger the culture is. Whether an administration's culture is strong, weak or somewhere in between, depends on factors such as the size of the administration, how long it has been around, how much turnover there has been among employees and the intensity with which the culture was originated. One study of administrative culture found that employees in firms with strong cultures were committed to their firm than were employees in firm than were employees in firms with weak cultures. The firms with strong cultures also used their recruitment efforts and socialization practices to build employee commitment. An increased body of evidence suggests that strong cultures are associated with high administrative performance.

7. CONCLUSION

The conventional view about culture and climate is that they exist at different levels. Culture is usually taken to be very deeply embedded in subconsciously held values, beliefs and have basic assumptions and so many administrative members that might not be aware that a culture exists let alone how it affects their behavior. Conversely, climate tends to be regarded as more of a surface phenomenon, with easily identifiable effects on behavior. Although subculture can exist within administrations, culture tends to be viewed as a persuasive phenomenon, whereas micro climate tends to be regarded as more investable because many of the important factors directly influence climatic conditions in which the group is located. The antecedents of climates are better understood and it is usually assumed that climates change more quickly than cultures.

REFERENCES: -

- Balshlow SC (1999). *Traditional Exchange and Modern Markets*: New York Prentice Hall.
- Banting P.G. (1996). *Customer Service in Industrial Marketing*, New York McGraw Hill.
- Borch F.J. (1991). *The Marketing Philosophy as a Way of Building Life*, New York, American Management Association.
- Buzzell R. D. (1978). *Product Profitability Measurement and Merchandising Decisions*, Boston Harvard University, Press.
- Greer T. V. (1988) *Marketing in the Soviet Union*, New York, Holt Rinchart and Winston.
- Kotler P. (1980). *Principles of Marketing*, Prentice Hall International.
- Journal of Comprehensive Research, Volume 8, Page 18 Organisational Behavior
- Revzan D.A. (1981). *Wholesaling in Marketing Administrations*, New York, John Wiley.
- Rom J. and Markin J.R. (1994). *Consumer Behavior: Cognitive Orientation*, New York, MacMillan.
- Stanton W.J. (1992). *Fundamentals of Marketing. (5th Edition)*, New York, McGraw Hill.